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Stirling approximation for the Gamma function

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October 28, 2024

Abstract

We present an approximation for the gamma function using Stirling's formula and, as a consequence, we obtain an asymptotic approximation for the factorial of a positive real number.

keywords: gamma function, Stirling's formula, factorial

The most updated version of this white paper is available at
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14002466>

Introduction

1. This article primarily relies on references [1, 2].
2. Stirling's formula is an asymptotic approximation mainly used for large values of positive integers, both in the calculation of the factorial and in the study of the gamma function.
3. Stirling's formula is fundamental in asymptotic analysis, as it offers a way to approximate the behavior of rapidly growing functions, such as the factorial and the gamma function, simplifying complex expressions involving these functions.

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4. In this article, we will prove that Stirling's formula can be extended to provide an approximation for the gamma function when its argument is a sufficiently large positive real number. In this way, it will be possible to obtain an asymptotic approximation for the factorial of that number.

Preliminaries

Gamma Function

5. The function $\Gamma : (0, +\infty) \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$, defined by

$$\Gamma(x) = \int_0^{+\infty} t^{x-1} e^{-t} dt$$

is called the Gamma function.

Properties

6. For any positive real number x , we have the recurrence relation:

$$\Gamma(x + 1) = x\Gamma(x).$$

7. For any integer n , the Gamma function is related to the factorial by:

$$\Gamma(n) = (n - 1)!$$

8. We can define the factorial of a positive real number x in terms of the Gamma function:

$$x! = \Gamma(x + 1).$$

The Gamma Function and Stirling's Formula

9. Two functions $g, h : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are asymptotically equal if

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{g(x)}{h(x)} = 1.$$

10. If g and h are asymptotically equal functions, we can write:

$$g(x) \sim h(x).$$

11. The symbol “ \sim ” means “is asymptotically (or approximately) equal to, for large x ”.

12. **Lema A.** For $x \in \mathbb{R}$, with $x > 0$,

$$\int_0^{+\infty} e^{\left[-\frac{(t-x)^2}{2x}\right]} dt \cong \sqrt{2\pi x}.$$

13. Indeed, we identify

$$u = \frac{t-x}{\sqrt{2x}}.$$

14. Note that

$$du = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2x}} dt.$$

15. When $t = 0$, $u = -\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}$, and when $t \rightarrow +\infty$, $u \rightarrow +\infty$.

16. Now, substituting these values into the integral,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{\left[-\frac{(t-x)^2}{2x}\right]} dt &= \int_{-\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}}^{+\infty} e^{(-u^2)} \cdot \sqrt{2x} du \\ &= \sqrt{2x} \cdot \int_{-\sqrt{\frac{x}{2}}}^{+\infty} e^{(-u^2)} du. \end{aligned}$$

17. This last integral is the Gaussian integral, which involves the *complementary error function* (see [2]), defined by

$$\operatorname{Erfc}(y) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_y^{\infty} e^{(-t^2)} dt.$$

18. The complementary error function has the following property:

$$\operatorname{Erfc}(-y) = 2 - \operatorname{Erfc}(y).$$

19. Using this property into (16), we obtain

$$\int_0^{+\infty} e^{\left[-\frac{(t-x)^2}{2x}\right]} dt = \frac{\sqrt{2\pi x}}{2} \left[2 - \operatorname{Erfc}\left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{2}\right) \right].$$

20. Therefore,

$$\int_0^{+\infty} e^{\left[-\frac{(t-x)^2}{2x}\right]} dt \cong \sqrt{2\pi x}.$$

□

21. **Theorem (Main result).** Let x be a positive real number. Then, the Gamma function can be approximated by

$$\Gamma(x+1) \sim \sqrt{2\pi x} \left(\frac{x}{e}\right)^x.$$

Consequently, we have the approximation

$$x! \sim \sqrt{2\pi x} \left(\frac{x}{e}\right)^x.$$

22. Indeed, let x be a positive real number. Consider the Gamma function

$$\Gamma(x+1) = \int_0^{+\infty} t^{x-1} e^{-t} dt.$$

23. We define the function $f(t) = x \ln(t) - t$ for $t \in (0, +\infty)$.

24. Thus,

$$\Gamma(x+1) = \int_0^{+\infty} e^{f(t)} dt = \int_0^{+\infty} e^{x \ln(t) - t} dt.$$

25. Since $f'(x) = 0$, $t = x$ is a critical point of f .

26. Now, consider the Taylor expansion of f around $t = x$

$$f(t) \cong f(x) + \frac{f''(x)}{2} (t-x)^2.$$

27. Substituting $f(x)$ and $\frac{f''(x)}{2} = -\frac{1}{2x}$, we obtain the approximation

$$f(t) \cong x \ln(x) - x - \frac{1}{2x} (t-x)^2.$$

28. Using this approximation into (24), we have

$$\Gamma(x+1) \cong x^x \cdot e^{-x} \cdot \int_0^{+\infty} e^{\left[-\frac{(t-x)^2}{2x}\right]} dt.$$

29. Therefore, by Lemma A presented in (12),

$$\Gamma(x + 1) \sim \sqrt{2\pi x} \left(\frac{x}{e}\right)^x .$$

30. On the other hand, from (8), we obtain

$$x! \sim \sqrt{2\pi x} \left(\frac{x}{e}\right)^x .$$

□

Final Remarks

31. This article presented a generalized explicit solution for the improper integral of a rational function whose denominator is a polynomial of even degree, using the Residue Theorem. By applying fundamental concepts from Complex Analysis, it was possible to simplify and solve the problem, contributing to the study of improper integrals and to the understanding of the interactions between rational functions and their complex poles.
32. The developed method can be applied to various problems involving improper integrals of rational functions. Moreover, the application of the Residue Theorem in different contexts may inspire future research in areas where complex integration plays a significant role.

Open Invitation

*Review, add content to, and co-author this white paper [3,4].
Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Supplementary Files

[5]

How to Cite this White Paper

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14002466>

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Agreement

All authors are in agreement with the guidelines presented in [4].

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